

Beyond Statistical Significance: Problems and Pitfalls of Quantitative Research*

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Abstract

Null hypothetical statistical tests reign supreme in research in most all disciplines when statistical analysis is used. While popular, novice researchers struggle designing, reporting, and analyzing quantitative studies. Five common problems in research are p hacking, HARKing, common method bias, sample and instrument bias, and assumptions not reported. Robustness means statistical assumptions must be evaluated and decisions made, as most assumptions will differ from theoretical recommendations. Moving beyond the concept of statistical significance and the misuse of p values, researchers can improve the link between statistical tests and results. After discussing the five common problems, a matrix is presented to guide researchers in improving study design to simplify and strengthen design. A major improvement could be adopting a continuum of practical significance with three factors.

Keywords: doctoral students, quantitative methodologies, research design, statistical analysis, practical significance

"Modern statisticians are familiar with the notion that any finite body of data contains only a limited amount of information on any point under examination; that this limit is set by the nature of the data themselves, and cannot be increased by any amount of ingenuity expended in their statistical examination: that the statistician's task, in fact, is limited to the extraction of the whole of the available information on any particular issue."

➤ Ronald Fisher

"Without data, you are just another person with an opinion."

➤ William Edwards Deming

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Quiz #1

A student conducted a t-test to determine whether an intervention makes a difference using an experimental and control group. Answers and discussion are towards the end of the introduction.

1. TRUE or FALSE The p value is .051, so there is no difference between groups.
2. TRUE or FALSE The findings are important because the results are highly statistically significant.
3. TRUE or FALSE Confidence intervals prove the range of values that are true.
4. TRUE or FALSE With a p value of .01, the alternative hypothesis is proven correct.
5. TRUE or FALSE A low p value shows that the intervention worked.

Note. Hoekstra et al. (2014) were used for part of the quiz.

Introduction

A shocking truth that beguiles research today: *Everything can be manipulated to reject the null hypothesis. Cut a sample small enough or run enough tests, and the results will be what one wants.* Seemingly, in the social sciences, everything works no matter what is done, even if the results are contradictory (Coker, 2022). Researchers know to avoid null findings, as there is a greatly decreased chance of getting published (Franco et al., 2014). Read most every dissertation and published article, and by a wide margin, the researchers found not only what they were looking for but the coveted statistically significant result, where the p value was less than .05.

Dissertation chairs commonly hear the following refrain from students: “The study is no good because I did not find statistically significant results.” Herndon (2016) pointed out that researchers are under intense pressure to publish or perish, so everything from fabricating data to using a test for a desired finding is a problem in academia. A problem is that researchers often create a post hoc literature review, rationale, and questions that are used to select datasets and tests that report significant findings (Luck & Gaspelin, 2017). The researchers in question are not necessarily unscrupulous, as Herndon (2016) points out: Ignorance and mistakes can be the culprit.

All the answers in the quiz are false or, with a statistical flare, uncertain. Each question pertains to common problems encountered by researchers in designing and reporting results; the same problems exist from dissertations to peer reviewed articles. Null hypothesis significance tests (NHST), such as t-tests and ANOVA, are commonly used in research studies. Statistical significance tells nothing about practical significance, though many dissertations depend on getting the desired p value. No difference because the p-value is over the predetermined limit is generally not true, as two samples are rarely precisely the same. Rejecting or accepting the null hypothesis does not prove something worked, and statisticians must be careful about claims of certainty. Confidence intervals do not prove anything about the qualitative nature of a study succeeding/failing, as they show the likely true value and precision by estimating a range.

The chapter proceeds in three sections. First, common statistical tests and how to report them are presented to assist researchers in conducting statistical tests. Secondly, common problems in quantitative analysis are reported, with possible solutions. One major shift is overtly applying inferential causation to every study. A method for practical significance guides researchers in qualifying and quantifying results. Finally, a matrix guides researchers in designing a quantitative research study. New and experienced researchers will have a guide to improve their research design, data collection, analysis, and write-ups.

Common Statistical Tests

Stanley Pogrow and others in textbooks point out something many novice researchers do not know: Simpler is better, and one generally only needs a high school understanding to run a statistical test. Besides, most statistical tests will never be run by hand, though it is a good practice to conduct simple computations by hand to truly understand how the different statistics work. After briefly reviewing the basics of statistics and common tests, three major points can improve a researcher's practice: fully reporting results, using robustness to understand assumptions, and inferential causation.

The most common inferential statistical tests in dissertations are chi square, t test, ANOVA, correlation, and linear regression. Preparing the data includes examining the data for accuracy, dealing with missing values (either dropping or imputation), reverse scoring if applicable, and creating the proper format (long and wide format, with wide most common for the aforementioned tests). Researchers must start with descriptive statistics to give readers an understanding of the distribution of the data. Visualizing the data with scatterplots, histograms, and box and whisker plots is recommended to start with inspection. Range, mean (M), median, and standard deviation (SD) are common, and all provide a visualization of the data. (The mean is generally the arithmetic mean unless otherwise specified). Failing to report completely the descriptive statistics can be misleading. For example, reporting $M = 19.42$ gives little information compared to the following three scenarios: A.) $M = 19.42$; $SD = 0.25$; B.) $M = 19.42$; $SD = 2.50$; $M = 19.42$; $SD = 6.32$. The SD tells a much different story about the spread, or dispersion, of the data (the median would also help describe the distribution, as would the range).

Researchers follow some or all of the following assumptions using the acronym O'HIMNLS (sounds like o' hymnal, with a hymn being a song): outliers, homogeneity of variance/homoscedasticity, multicollinearity, normality, linearity, and singularity. Outliers are data that do not follow the normal distribution of the data, with various sources recommending anywhere from 2-3 SD away from the mean; outliers are sometimes caused by erroneously entering the information. Homogeneity of variance (homoscedasticity is the sister term, though it is in multiple regression and for the residuals) means the different groups have similar distributions. Independence is a requirement for most tests. Multicollinearity is used in multiple regression and other techniques to check if two variables are highly correlated where they might be measuring the same variable. Normality is examining if data follows the test's required distribution, an assumption of parametric tests (though in multiple regression, normality is checked for the error terms). Linearity is a requirement in correlation and regression. Finally, singularity is extreme multicollinearity, where often two variables or either the same or one is part of another.

Researchers should understand robustness, or the ability of a statistic to be accurate—that is not biased—when assumptions are violated. If, like most students, a variety of tests are recommended to examine each issue, such as Shapiro-Wilk's, Levene's, Cook's distance, etc. However, outside of theoretical statistics, data rarely follows any assumption perfectly. Another issue is that many tests to check for assumptions are themselves sensitive and possibly biased, too conservative, and problematic depending on sample size. Many researchers make the mistake of using assumptions like a checklist, and then when something is violated, continuing even though early the assumptions were promulgated as required. A better way is to understand and apply the concept of robustness, which can vary by test.

Some general rules are that larger samples are more robust than smaller samples (e.g., a sample of 10 with 2 outliers will not perform as well as a sample of 50 with 2 outliers, etc.). Correlation and regression do not perform well when the data is nonlinear. The t-test and ANOVA are robust to violations of the different assumptions, with the following caveats: extremely skewed populations, violations of homogeneity of variance/different sample sizes, and outliers (Blanca Mena et al., 2017; Stonehouse & Forrester, 1998). Welch's versions for the t-test and ANOVA are possibilities for violations of homogeneity of variance and different sample sizes. Robustness depends on sample sizes and the condition of the data to determine the breakpoint. When there are outliers, sometimes one will have to move to nonparametric tests and/or transform the data. Researchers will generally only face these problems with small samples. Statistical packages and websites also offer the possibility of conducting a statistical test by the number

needed to produce the desired p-value (interesting how sometimes removing 1 or 2 values can make the desired statistically significant result disappear). In any manner, robustness and assumptions must be judged on an individual basis and transparently reported.

Every researcher, from the absolute beginner to the seasoned professional, has heard the adage: Correlation is not causation. Yet, nothing could be further from the truth in academia. *Every* inferential statistic is used to tell a story of causation, and the correct interpretation is that correlation implies causation (Kuang et al., 2020). While Kuang spoke about engineering, the social sciences can be much messier, giving researchers the chance to miss confounders, lurking variables, and spurious relationships. Nevertheless, a priori, researchers must construct models based on prior theory and findings to generate relationships that can be inferred as causal in nature. Researchers must be industrious to report possible alternatives, needs for future research, and practical implications. Grosz et al. (2020) provide the best advice: Be open and explicit about theorized causal mechanisms at play, with clear processes and assumptions stated. Readers can then judge the research and findings.

Inferential causation is the reason for a hypothesis and should be discussed in the results. Most researchers make the mistake of believing in a direct cause, or $A \rightarrow B$. In most all cases involving human research, the linkage between a variable of interest and an outcome is much messier, as shown in Table 1. Two common problems exist: Multifinality, where the same paths lead to many outcomes, and equifinality, where regardless of previous variables, the same outcome happens. Researchers should be open to missing causes, whether extraneous variables are not included or different relationships, as well as classic ways of threats to internal validity, such as maturation, mortality, history, lack of a control group, and biases (e.g., Hawthorne effect, John Henry effect, etc.).

Table 1. Relationships in causation.

Hypothetical: The researcher conducted a t-test on participants in a spelling bee, comparing the winners and losers as the two groups and separating them by high grit versus low grit on a survey instrument. The winners had a statistically significant difference with higher grit than the losers.

Causal Mechanism	Diagram	Explanation
Direct Effect	$A \rightarrow B$	Grit \rightarrow Winning, or higher grit causes one to excel.
Indirect Moderator/Mediator	Effect: $A \rightarrow ??? \rightarrow B$	Grit \rightarrow Moderator \rightarrow Winning or Grit \rightarrow Mediator \rightarrow Winning, or grit causes winning only when a moderator is present or is influenced by a mediator.
Reverse Effect	$A \leftarrow B$	Winning \rightarrow Grit, or the relationship is reversed, as winning improves grit
Reciprocal Effect	$A \leftrightarrow B$	Grit $\leftarrow \rightarrow$ Winning, or both work to increase each other (e.g., grit leads to improvements and winning leads to grit, etc.).
Spurious Effect	$A \& B$	Grit and Winning are not related even though differences exist (e.g., lurking variables, i.e., winners feel elated and believe they tried harder, etc.).

Common Problems

P Hacking. P hacking is designing studies to find a statistically significant effect. If one has ever tried to publish null findings in major journals, one knows they are rejected en masse because publishers want positive findings. Common methods to get a desired p value include manipulating samples (omitting values, increasing size, dividing into new subgroups, etc.), transforming data, selecting a new test, binning the data, and including new variables (Motulsky, 2014). Part of the problem is relying on p values as the only metric; it is common to state $p = .0499$ as statistically significant and expound a major difference, yet $p = .0501$ is erroneously described as no difference and not significant.

Another major concern is that p values are inversely related to sample size. For example, a reading test administered to two groups, one with 10 students and 100, gives a very different p value when the t-test is used. If one group scored an average of 82 and another 80, with an SD of 5.00, the group with 10 total (5 in each group) has $t = 0.632$, $df = 8$, and $p = .5447$ —not the coveted statistically significant desired by most researchers. The second t-test is identical in mean/SD but has 50 in each group: $t = 2.00$, $df = 98$, and $p = .0483$ —a statistically significant result.

P values matter—that is why NHST are conducted—but they do not tell the entire story. Greenland et al. (2016) recommended, at minimum, reporting p-values, confidence intervals, sample size, and effect size. Giving a holistic picture of the results always requires an interpretation. A major problem is moving beyond statistical significance to practical significance. Research is littered with examples of “highly statistically significant” results being trivial and no noticeable improvement.

Practical significance is how demonstrably results are not only different but better and should be explicitly described. To accomplish this task, a continuum of outcomes, as shown in Figure 1, needs to be developed. Researchers can start with the following question to ascertain practical significance considering a model: At what level of change is there a visible and valuable difference? Most everything in the social sciences has some type of association, and with a large enough sample, a statistically significant effect can be found. What that means, though, must be qualified and quantified.

Factors: Costs-----Time-----Benefits (individual & group)

Negative Effect Small to No Effect Positive Effect

Figure 1. Continuum of Practical Significance

Three factors should comprise the continuum: costs, time, and benefits. Costs and time give input into return on investment. Benefits need to be dissected at the individual and group level by the positive, neutral, and negative. Computing the number needed to treat and plotting by histogram the actual scores post-intervention on the continuum would extend the results at an individual level, as the group benefit might be illusory for some or most individuals (Pogrow, 2020, emphasizes examining descriptive statistics to ascertain what real changes happen). One can see the continuum of practical significance using the example of the fictional reading score with a control and experimental group, which, in the sample of 100, was statistically significant and raised reading scores from 80 to 82. Cohen’s *d* for effect size would be

0.40, which is often suggested as moderate. The confidence interval is 0.02-3.98 at the 95% level. Both numbers add to the debate, but the effect size might be misleading.

Researchers would need to judge what would be an acceptable minimum benefit by plotting how different results would be negative, no/little, or positive effects. Baseline would be an important factor in such analysis. What would be the benefits and costs of a reading program that raised scores by 2 points? First, the instrumentation error and validity/reliability mean the difference could be error, and the distribution of improvement might create a vastly different picture (e.g., changing 2 scores might erase the desired p value or a small number of outliers reveal little improvement for most, etc.). Secondly, would changing an entire program for 2 points be worth the time and money? Thirdly, what would be a significant practical benefit? A desired score of 90? Changing a subgroup that failed? Ease of use and a general but very small benefit? In this case, 82 might be a little different than no intervention, though the individual improvements might shift this analysis, the effect size cannot be gauged by a rule of thumb, and purchasing a reading intervention that produces little to no widespread improvement would not be advisable based only on a statistically significant finding that might be superfluous.

Samples and Instruments. Researchers must describe the sampling method, the sample, and the population. The main purpose of inferential statistics is to generalize beyond the selected sample, so researchers should describe the relationship between the sample and the population. Samples will always have errors and biases, so researchers should be upfront about what the sample comprises. A second concern is that all instruments have errors themselves and are often misused. Academic and intelligence tests, as well as instruments such as blood pressure cuffs, have errors that mean due to lack of precision, a small difference might be noise. A 100 and a 101 on an IQ test or blood pressures of 122/80 and 120/80 might be real or by error (not to mention determining what, if any, practical significance).

Researchers need to clearly specify sampling procedures, sample characteristics, and the population. Nonrandom and small samples have limited generalizability and transferability. Baseline analysis, or how compared samples are similar, is often overlooked in analysis. The What Works Clearinghouse (WWC) has procedures to compare baseline equivalency; comparing two dissimilar groups with an intervention means an extraneous variable might be a confounder. Instruments used have limitations that statistical tests do not capture, so researchers must review and report reliability, validity, and potential error to contextualize results.

HARKing. Hypothesizing after results are known is a major problem in all research, especially exploratory research. HARKing can either result in reformulating hypotheses after results or unethical changes in research design, sampling, and tests to arrive at desired results and pretend the new results were the aim of the study. A significant driver of HARKing is that researchers want to appear correct and produce positive results, as null findings are not only seen as a failure but also decrease the likelihood of publication.

Two aspects can avoid the HARKing dilemma. First, null findings are important findings. Report them, and realize that not finding a difference or effect is as important as positive findings. Secondly, researchers can hypothesize after results are known, but researchers must be transparent about why there was a shift in procedures.

Common method bias. Common method bias refers to errors inherent in the instruments and methods used, from the instrument design to cognitive biases by respondents (Podsakoff et al., 2003). While common method bias can be complex, two simple factors should be considered in the design and mitigation: Are participants meeting researcher expectations in their responses? Is data from a single source and/or single sample?

Researchers should consider biases from all angles of the research process. For example, participants are commonly asked to report satisfaction in a program/intervention, but there is evidence that participants often like attention no matter what. Another issue is that examining a construct in the same way as previous research will perpetuate existing errors, so researchers can use different samples, blind the study's aims, and incorporate more than one instrument.

Report all assumptions. Most statistics have assumptions, including nonparametric tests. Results are valid under assumptions but can be biased or plain wrong when assumptions are violated. In the real world, apart from theoretical statistics, assumptions will always be negotiated—a nice way to say violations at some level will exist. Reporting descriptive and inferential statistics fully and thoroughly allows readers to make their own decisions.

Parametric and nonparametric statistical tests have assumptions and requirements that describe biases and errors. Determining a study's power, sample sufficiency, and sample representativeness informs readers about generalizability, transferability, and limitations. What was done and the decisions made should be listed in full. Statistics is part art, part science, and results require the human factor.

Design Matrix

Researchers should consider the alignment of research design as a holistic process, as shown in Table 2. All samples, no matter how large, randomized, and/or well-defined, are used for point estimates that have error and limited generalizability. Null findings do not prove the absence of a result but provide evidence for further study. Mapping the process before starting can save time in having to go back and collect more data, improving data collection, and formatting.

Table 2. Research Design Matrix

1.	Purpose and Aims	The purpose and aims should be operationalized, and the end result must match.
2.	Research Questions	The research questions must be manageable, answerable, and measurable. Operationalization of variables and a hypothesis should be identified at this stage. Expected statistical tests and alternatives (sample size, distribution, and variables might preclude the primary choice) are chosen for the study.
3.	Sample	Availability is the first concern, followed by sampling methods, sample size, sample representativeness, and population, which are minimum requirements. Collecting enough demographic data to describe a sample is often overlooked. The sample size must be large enough to conduct the requisite tests.
4.	Data Collection	Demographic data sufficient to explain and explore the study must be mapped. Manifest and latent variables must be measurable and with a degree of precision.
5.	Data Analysis	Inputting the data in the correct form and checking for accuracy should be planned and reported. Each statistical test depends on assumptions and comparisons with a population. Alternative tests and data formats should be considered if needed. Full reporting of data handling, problems, complete test statistics, p values, confidence intervals, effect size, etc. Any deviations or new hypotheses should be reported and justified.
6.	Parsimonious	The more complex, the more variables, and more interactions all increase error and shrink reliability. Researchers must strive for the simplest results that adequately describe a phenomenon.
7.	Limitations	Limitations are unplanned problems that limit validity and introduce biases. Researchers should fully explore alternatives and issues with a study. Samples, instruments, and tests all limit the results.
8.	Inferential Causation	What practical and/or predictive significance is there? All studies are designed under the belief that there is a theoretical and/or practical cause-

and-effect relationship. Researchers should fully explore inferential causation and map alternative possibilities.

Summary

- ✓ Null findings are as important as positive findings.
- ✓ Certainty is an illusion, and all statistical models are oversimplifications applicable to a specific sample and population at one point in time.
- ✓ Report descriptive statistics and all assumptions.
- ✓ Decide if the results accurately describe the trends in the data.
- ✓ Use visuals where possible to report descriptive and inferential statistics.
- ✓ Move beyond p values by reporting all test statistics, confidence intervals, and effect sizes.
- ✓ Practical significance is a qualitative measure if a difference has any real-world or predictive effect. Researchers should use a continuum and consider costs, time, and benefits/harm.
- ✓ Consider reporting the minimum number in the study that, if different, would negate the statistical significance.
- ✓ All studies should have a pilot, where either a small sample is used or a researcher conducts a fictional study and analyzes the data.

Recommended Readings

We learn statistics by doing. Start running tests, even with small samples, using events in your life. Here are recommendations to get started for free today:

JASP, a free program similar to SPSS. <https://jasp-stats.org/download/>

G*Power, a free program to determine sample size and power. <https://www.psychologie.hhu.de/arbeitsgruppen/allgemeine-psychologie-und-arbeitspsychologie/gpower>

Daniel Soper, a great website to practice different tests. <https://www.danielsoper.com/>

The chi-square test seems so simple, what could go wrong? This article provides a brief primer on what to do and what to avoid.

Franke, T. M., Ho, T., & Christie, C. A. (2012). The chi-square test: Often used and more often misinterpreted. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 33(3), 448-458.

Planning a dissertation with the end in mind improves the entire process. The rubric can be used to plan any study.

Coker, D. C. (2022). A thematic analysis of the structure of delimitations in the dissertation. *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*, 17, 141-159. <https://doi.org/10.28945/4939>

The best introductory text to understanding the basics of probability.

Caldwell, S. (2012). *Statistics unplugged*. Wadsworth Publishing.

With Healey, researchers will be equipped to conduct most statistical tests. The book is thorough, insightful, and easy to understand for non-math majors.

Healey, J. F. (2013). *The essentials of statistics: A tool for social research*. Wadsworth Publishing.

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Though the following article is focused on medicine, any reader can use the errors in their own design, results, and reporting.

Lang, T. (2004). Twenty statistical errors even you can find in biomedical research articles. *Croatian Medical Journal*, 45(4), 361-370.

Motulsky simplifies problems where they are easily understood and can be applied to one's own research.
Motulsky, H. J. (2014). Common misconceptions about data analysis and statistics. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 351(1), 200-205. <https://doi.org/10.1007%2Fs00210-014-1037-6>

Baseline equivalence is often overlooked in research design.

What Works Clearinghouse. *Baseline equivalence.*
https://ies.ed.gov/ncee/wwc/Docs/referenceresources/wwc_brief_baseline_080715.pdf

A great explanation of effect size and how to select one for a test.

Lakens, D. (2013). Calculating and reporting effect sizes to facilitate cumulative science: A practical primer for t-tests and ANOVAs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 863. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00863>

A great book on the entire process of a quantitative dissertation. Readers might be surprised to learn why complex statistical tests often lack value.

Pogrow, S. (2018). *Authentic quantitative analysis for education leadership decision-making and EdD dissertations: A practical, intuitive, and intelligible approach: How to critique and apply quantitative research to improve practice, and develop a rigorous and useful EdD dissertation.* ICPEL Publications.

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